

A2IM: Cookbook

Test Geometry

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose of Document

A goal in the Opticon A²IM project was to develop an Additive Manufacturing benchmark part:

- to analyse the capabilities of various Additive Manufacturing technologies concerning the geometric accuracy and create design guidelines based on the results.
- to evaluate a new material, process or parameters.
- to create awareness for design engineers and operators.

The test geometry could be used to compare systems and materials and to see if this design is appropriate for those processes as well. The idea is to provide designers and engineers a real production case build on multiple processes and materials and help them to improve the quality of new concepts and parts.

2 APPLICABLE AND REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

2.1 Applicable Documents

The following documents are also deliverables of the OPTICON WP5, and combined, form the reference material undertaken within the project.

Table 1: Reference Documents

Ref No	Document type	Document Title	Year
A1	A2IM report	A2IM Cookbook	2021
A2	A2IM report	Report on Additive Manufacturing Materials for OPTICON Work Package 5.1.1	2020

2.2 Reference Documents

The following documents provide useful reference information associated with this document. These documents are to be used for information only. Changes to the date and/or revision number do not make this document out of date.

Table 2: Reference Documents

Ref No	Document/Drawing Number	Document Title	Issue Number
01	Conference Proceeding	H. Schnetler et al., 'H2020 opticon WP5 overview: investigating the use of additive manufacturing AM for the design and build of multifunctional integrated astronomical components', Proc. SPIE 11451	2020
02	3D CAD File Opticon Test Geometry.STL	Thingiverse	2021
03	3D CAD File Opticon Test Geometry.STEP	GrabCad	2021
04	3D CAD File Opticon Test Geometry.SLDPRT	3D Content Central	2021

3 THE OPTICON PROJECT

The Opticon A²IM project kicked-off at the start of 2017 and we set out to investigate the use of additive manufacturing (also known as 3-D printing) for the fabrication of multi-functional astronomical components. A multifunctional component is a single component, which implements more than one function at a time. For example, an optical trombone can be used to redirect science light and it can compensate for path-length variations at the same time.

During 2017 and 2018, the team undertook a feasibility study. Firstly, the team prepared a list of frequently used astronomical components. For each component, the typical features and requirements have been identified. This was followed by the designing of a benchmark model or Test geometry that allowed us to define the limits for each of the most promising materials and 3-D printing processes. A detailed description of the test geometry is given in this document. Each benchmark part produced was visually inspected and measured.

On completion of the feasibility study, a study report was prepared. The report can be downloaded from <https://www.astro-opticon.org/h2020/public-reports.html>

After the feasibility study, the team elected to focus on the integration of special features and mirrors that can be used in astronomical instruments such as imagers and spectrographs. Some of these components are displayed in figure 1. The initial idea was to qualify these mirrors for cryogenic operations. Unfortunately, due to limited access to laboratories, the team has not managed to proceed as initially planned. We have received a no-cost extension until June 2021, however at this moment in time; nobody is sure, when things will return to normal.

FAME mirror
AM design: Konkoly

Ceramic Mirror
AM design: LAM

Topology optimised Amplified
Actuator
AM design: STFC

SiSiC mirror –
AM design: IAC

Figure 1: An overview of 3D printed optical components developed in the A²IM project. The parts are designed and engineered keeping Additive Manufacturing design rules in mind (image credits: TNO)

4 OPTICON TEST GEOMETRY

4.1 Standards and Norms

Current AM standards Working groups for the development of AM-related standards have been organized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO/TC 261) and the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM F42). To date, they have produced standards related to terminology, individual processes, chains of processes (hardware and software), test procedures, quality parameters, customer-supplier agreements, and fundamental elements. Recent additions address data processing and consider the relevance of and specify variations to existing standards. In 2013, ISO and ASTM defined a common goal to produce one set of global standards including general standards that are applicable to most AM materials, processes, and applications; category standards that define the requirements for a material or a process category; and specialized standards for specific requirements to a material, process or application. AM standardization efforts are also taking place in:

- Germany (VDI FA 105 and DIN NA 145-04-01AA),
- Spain (AEN/CTN 116),
- France (AFNOR UNM 920),
- Sweden (SIS/TK 563),
- US (SAE AMS-AM)
- UK (BSI AMT/8)

The Association of German Engineers published VDI 3404 and VDI 3405 as part of this work. AM standards provide a common understanding of the field and a shared lexicon from which to work. This is important for developing and using AM-related design tools and methodologies. It is also a criterion for developing design related AM standards. For example, ISO/ASTM DIS 20195 “Guide for Design for Additive Manufacturing” is currently under development.

Figure 2: The last two decades various 3D printing benchmark and test artefacts have been introduced by several organisations and research institutes.

4.1.1 Inspirational bench mark parts

A new Opticon test geometry was designed to meet the requirements for lightweight and stiff optical components. Current available test artefacts from NIST and the DIN ISO ASTM 52902 standard inspired artefact from the University of Tirol were used as a guideline.

NIST artefact	University of Tirol Artefact (inspired by DIN EN ISO ASTM 52902)	3DBenchy
<p>National Institute of Standards and Technology Design: Shawn Moylan</p> <p>Available for download at NIST</p>	<p>University of Tirol Design: Markus Ehrlebenbach</p> <p>Available for download at Thingiverse and GrabCad</p>	<p>Design by Creative Tools</p> <p>Available for download at: 3dBenchy.com</p>

Figure 3: Current test artefacts used for benchmarking and round robin tests.

4.2 Opticon Test Geometry

Multiple design features are incorporated in the Opticon Test Geometry that will display the capabilities and limitations of the selected Additive Manufacturing technology. The round structure is divided in pie sections of 45° degrees. Each section is dedicated to a certain type of lattice structure or family of features.

Figure 4: The Opticon Test geometry with multiple features.

4.2.1 Specifications

Keeping the build volume of multiple high accurate AM processes in mind and limit the build time and expenses an outer dimension of $\varnothing 45 \times 12.5$ mm was selected. The current volume of the test geometry, including all lattice structures is approximately 7300 mm^3 with a surface area of 12600 mm^2 .

Figure 5: Technical drawing of the test geometry.

4.3 Multiple features

Various design features are implemented in the Opticon test geometry. The most interesting features are explained in the table.

<p>Chamfer 1.5 mm</p> <p>30°, 45°, 60°</p>	<p>Vertical holes Depth: 3mm</p> <p>∅ 0.25, ∅ 0.50, ∅ 0.75, ∅ 1.00, ∅ 2.00, ∅ 3.00</p>	<p>Vertical pillars Height: 3mm</p> <p>∅ 0.25, ∅ 0.50, ∅ 0.75, ∅ 1.00, ∅ 2.00, ∅ 3.00</p>	<p>Cube staircase Step size: 1 mm</p> <p>3x3 mm</p>
<p>Angular overhang 3 x 4.5mm</p> <p>Angle: 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°</p>	<p>Horizontal holes Depth: 1.5 mm</p> <p>∅ 0.25, ∅ 0.50, ∅ 1, ∅ 1.50, ∅ 2, ∅ 3, ∅ 4.50</p>	<p>Horizontal overhang Depth: 1.5 mm</p> <p>Width: 2, 4, 8 mm</p>	<p>Conical rectangular hole Depth: 4.5 mm</p> <p>1.5 to 0.56 mm</p>
<p>X & Y Wall thickness 3 x 3 mm</p> <p>Thickness: 0.23, 0.35, 0.5, 0.75, 1.00mm</p>	<p>Pyramids Step size: 1mm</p> <p>Size: 3x3, 2x2, 1x1</p>	<p>Pyramid style cavity Step size: 1mm</p> <p>Size: 3x3, 2x2, 1x1</p>	<p>Internal channel Diameter: ∅ 1 mm</p>

Table 3: Some of the features implement in the test geometry design.

4.4 Production of samples

There are various service provider with an online quotation and manufacturing portal. Some common one's are Materialise, Shapeways, 3DHubs, Sculpteo, e.g. These service providers use computer algorithms to automatically generate the cost price and to check the manufacturability. This to prevent miss-prints and disappoint. Due to the automated processes, the price range is usually lower than specialised Additive Manufacturing service bureau's. Usually no direct communication with the organisation and personnel is possible.

4.4.1 Online service bureaus

i.Materialise is the low entry online ordering platform from the service provider Materialise. The Belgium company was founded in 1990 and combines AM software development with one of the largest and most complete 3D printing facilities in the world. Another large manufacturing platform is the Dutch – American company Shapeways. They originated as a Royal Philips start-up in 2007. It is a technology platform in advance additive manufacturing solutions with over 10 different AM processes and numerous materials. Other large providers are 3DHubs /Protolab and Sculpteo.

The online manufacturing service from Materialise offers over 20 different materials from multiple production technologies.

At Shapeways, customers can select from 90 different materials from diverse additive manufacturing methods. Cost prices are display directly.

Figure 6: Screen capture of the online AM service bureaus, iMaterialise and ShapeWays

To verify the part integrity and the suitability for 3D printing the various online 3D printing bureaus have developed online checkers. Critical areas are visualised by accentuated colours.

Sculpteo Thin spot checker

i-materialise Wall Thickness analysis tool

Shapeways 3D Tools

Figure 7: Online automated part verification made possible by Sculpteo, iMaterialise and ShapeWays.

4.4.2 Certified Additive Manufacturing companies

For initial prototyping applications these companies are a good alternative and they deliver qualitative good parts. For certified end-part production additional communication with the service bureau is essential. Therefore it's recommended to build a relation with a trusted service provider. Multiple specialized companies can be found in Europe.

Company	Location	Specialty	Remarks
3T	UK	Metals	Large range of metals including Copper
ToolCraft	Germany	Metals	Large machine fleet. Including post-processing
FIT Technology	Germany	Metals & Polymers PBF, EBM, WAAM	Inconel, Hastalloy, Scalmalloy, Copper, Aluminum, Stainless Steel
Poly-Shape by AddUp	France	Metals	Multiple Including Post processing
Digital Metal	Sweden	Metals (binderJetting)	Stainless steel, Inconel, Copper
3DSYSTEMS (former Layerwise)	Belgium	Metals	Titanium and others
Dunlee	The Netherlands	Refractive Metals	Including Post processing Tungsten
Materialise	Belgium	Polymers	Largest machine fleet
FKM	Germany	PBF of polymers	PA6, 11, 12, TPU, PEEK
SGL Carbon	Germany	Ceramics	SiSiC – CarbonSiC
Admatec	The Netherlands	Ceramics	$Al_2O_3 - ZrO_2 - SiO_2$
Lithoz	Austria	Ceramics	$Al_2O_3 - Si_3N_4$

Table 4: List of Additive Manufacturing Service bureaus with specialisation.

4.5 Cost price indication

Several online platforms have been consulted for an estimated cost price indication of the Opticon Test Geometry. Multiple technologies and materials were selected that can be found in table . There is wide price range. Mainly caused by efficiency and the extent of communication.

Service Providers		Economical			Higher segment	
		iMaterialise i.materialise.com	ShapeWays www.shapeways.com	Sculpteo www.sculpteo.com	ProtoLabs www.protolab.co.uk	StratasysDirect stratasysdirect.com
Metals						
DMLS	Stainless Steel 316L	-	-	€ 199	€ 625 (fine res)	\$432
	Titanium TiAl6V4	€ 146	-	€ 240	€ 669 (fine res)	\$490
	Aluminium AlSi10Mg	€ 91	\$96 (Renishaw)	-	€ 149	\$465
	Aluminium AlSi7Mg0.6	-	-	€ 135	-	-
	Copper C18150	-	-	-	-	\$549
	Inconel IN625	-	-	-	-	\$465
BJ	Stainless 316L	€ 33	\$ 45	€ 50	-	-
Polymers						
MJF	PA12	€ 13	\$ 10	€ 10	€ 34	\$102
SLS	PA12	€ 13	\$ 10	€ 10 €16 (high res)	€ 75	\$ 50
SLA	Acrylic Resin	€ 27	\$ 42	€ 38	€ 140	\$ 74
Remarks						
		ex shipping cost ex VAT	ex shipping and handling cost	Ex VAT	Ex VAT and shipping cost	Ex VAT Shipping and handling cost

Table 5: Cost price indication between multiple materials and service bureau's (Q4-2020)

4.5.1 Cost Evaluation Tool

The from origin Finnish engineering company EttePlan has developed an online cost evaluation tool to evaluate Additive manufacturing business cases The program AMOTool gives a clear insight in the cost break-down, scale of larger numbers and influence of batch size.

Figure 8: The AMOTool Online cost evaluation tool from EttePlan

4.6 Production of demonstrators

Multiple Additive Manufacturing technologies are selected to print the test geometry. The samples are manufactured at service bureaus on standard process equipment and with certified materials using standard process settings. All samples are printed according the preferred XY build direction as stated on the test geometry. The samples are manufactured with essential support structure only to visualise the limitations of the processes. The price per part are commercial prices d.d. Q4-2020.

Figure 9: The different 3D printed Opticon Test Geometries

		AM Technology	Material	Grade	Process equipment	Price/p
Metals	01	Powder bed Fusion	Aluminium	AlSi10Mg	SLM Solutions SLM 500	415 EURO (375 GBP) ¹
	02	Powder Bed Fusion	Aluminium	AlSi10Mg	Concept Laser MLab-R	625 EURO (565 GBP) ²
	03	Powder Bed Fusion	Titanium	TiAl6V4	Concept Laser MLab-R	-
Polymers	04	Powder Bed Fusion	GF Nylon	PA12-GF	EOS P395	165 EURO (150 GBP) ¹
	05	Vat Photo Polymersation	Photocurable resin Acrylate	VisiJet Flex	3D Systems ProJet 6000	140 EURO (125 GBP) ¹
	06	Vat Photo Polymersation	Photocurable resin Acrylate	Bluestone	3D Systems Projet 6000	165 EURO (150 GBP) ¹
	07	Material Jetting	Photocurable resin Acrylate	Vero Clear	Stratasys Connex 350	In house process STFC
	08	Material Jetting	Photocurable resin Acrylate	Tango Black	Stratasys Connex 350	In house process STFC
	09	Vat Photo Polymersation	Photocurable Resin Acrylate	FLFlex 2	FormLabs 3	In house process TNO

¹ CA Models Limited ² Laser Prototypes Europe ltd

Table 6: Specification of the manufactured samples.

4.6.1 Print results

AM Technology			
Powder Bed Fusion Metal	<p data-bbox="1166 674 1437 741">TiAl6V4 Concept Laser – Mlab-R</p>		
Powder Bed Fusion Polymer	<p data-bbox="469 1039 596 1106">PA12 EOS – P395</p>		
Vat Photo Polymerisation	<p data-bbox="1193 1404 1410 1471">FormLabs FLEFlex 02 Formlabs 3</p>		
Material Jetting	<p data-bbox="788 1767 1050 1834">Tango Black Stratasys – Connex 350</p>		

Table 7: Isometric view of the printed test geometries.

4.7 Analysis of samples

Using macroscopy, microscopy and scanning electron Microscopy (SEM), the samples are analysed and photographed. The images are used to measure feature sizes and to capture print characteristics such as defects and surface quality.

Macroscopy

Missing elements

Surface quality

Deformations

Microscopy

Sagging and dross

Missing features

Residual material and support

Scanning Electron Microscopy

Surface structure

Features

Small features

Figure 10: Different assessment tools are utilised to visualize defects

Print issues can normally be divided in process and machine limitations. Process settings and material quality may also cause printing errors. Common problems in metal AM parts are sagging and dross formation.

4.7.1 Feature: Lateral Holes

In additive manufacturing the creation of horizontal holes and passages may cause issues if downfacing surfaces are not well supported.

Figure 11: Lateral holes.

Powder Bed Fusion *Industrial* – AlSi10Mg

Small holes display no clear definition and experience sagging. Larger holes display a tear shape geometry

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 1.50 mm	Ø 2.00 mm
not present	Blocked	Open	Open	Open	Open
-	-	0.3 mm	0.6 mm	1.1 mm	1.5 mm

Powder Bed Fusion *High Resolution* – AlSi10Mg

Small holes display oval shape definition due to sagging. Larger holes are defined but experience sagging.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 1.50 mm	Ø 2.00 mm
Detectable but blocked	Open	Open	Open	Open	Open
-	0.22 mm	0.44 mm	0.6 mm	1.24 mm	1.64 mm

Powder Bed Fusion – TiAl6V4

Small holes display oval shape definition due to sagging. Larger holes are defined and experience limited sagging.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 1.50 mm	Ø 2.00 mm
Detectable But Blocked	Open 0.3 mm	Open 0.60 mm	Open 0.8 mm	Open 1.3 mm	Open 1.8 mm

Powder Bed Fusion – PolyAmide PA12

Small holes display clear definition and experience no sagging. Horizontal ceiling defined by layer thickness

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 1.50 mm	Ø 2.00 mm
not present	Open 0.25 mm	Open 0.5 mm	Open 0.8 mm	Open 1.2 mm	Open 1.5 mm

Vat Photo Polymerisation - VisiJet

Small holes display clear definition and experience no sagging. Larger holes display slight sagging. Support structure present in hole 1.5 and 2.0 mm

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 1.50 mm	Ø 2.00 mm
Blocked	Open 0.5 mm	Open 0.7 mm	Open 1.0 mm	Blocked Support 1.5 mm	Blocked Support 2.0 mm

Material Jetting – Objet Vero Clear

Small hole display blockage. Larger holes have clear definition. Some soluble support residue left. Clear marks of support structure on vertical side walls.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 1.50 mm	Ø 2.00 mm
Present	Open	Open	Open	Open	Open
Blocked	0.36 mm	0.6 mm	0.8 mm	1.2 mm	1.8

Vat Photo Polymerisation – FormLabs Flex2

All holes are present and open. Larger holes have clear definition. Smaller holes are oval.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 1.50 mm	Ø 2.00 mm
Open	Open	Open	Open	Open	Open
0.28 mm	0.48 mm	0.8 mm	1.0 mm	1.54 mm	2.06

4.7.2 Evaluation: Lateral holes

All processes display an amount of sagging and none of the holes are perfectly round. The metal processes also display dross formation at the top. Residual material and over curing of photocurable resin causes blockage of the small Ø0.25 mm hole.

4.8 Feature: Vertical holes

Vertical holes and passages are in general of better quality in additive manufacturing than horizontal ones.

Figure 12: Vertical holes (Z-direction)

Powder Bed Fusion *Industrial* – AlSi10Mg

Small holes display no clear definition. Top surface topology displays waviness.

ϕ 0.25 mm	ϕ 0.50 mm	ϕ 0.75 mm	ϕ 1.00 mm	ϕ 2.00 mm	ϕ 3.00 mm
Location Present	open	open	open	open	open
Small dimples	0.38 mm	0.68 mm	1.0 mm	1.94 mm	2.98 mm

Powder Bed Fusion *High Resolution* – AlSi10Mg

Small holes are present and display clear definition. Top surface topology is flat. Scanlines are clearly visible

ϕ 0.25 mm	ϕ 0.50 mm	ϕ 0.75 mm	ϕ 1.00 mm	ϕ 2.00 mm	ϕ 3.00 mm
present	open	open	open	open	open
0.20 mm	0.54 mm	0.74 mm	0.98 mm	2.0 mm	2.94 mm

Powder Bed Fusion – TiAl6V4

Small holes are present and display clear definition. Top surface topology is flat. Some scanlines are missing.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
Present 0.18 mm	Present 0.46 mm	open 0.72 mm	Open 0.9 mm	Open 2.0 mm	Open 3.02 mm

Powder Bed Fusion – PolyAmide PA12

Small vertical holes are not present or blocked by residual powder. Large holes also display presence of residual powder.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
not present -	not present -	blocked -	blocked -	Open 1.86 mm	Open 2.84 mm

Vat Photo Polymerisation - VisiJet

Small holes are present but blocked. Clear definition

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
Location Present Blocked	blocked -	blocked 0.64 mm	Open 0.98 mm	Open 2.0 mm	Open 3.0 mm

Material Jetting – Objet Vero Clear

Small holes display blockage. Larger holes have clear definition. Rounded edges can be detected

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
Not present Small dimples	Open 0.5 mm	open 0.78 mm	Open 1.05 mm	Open 2.08 mm	Open 3.0 mm

Vat Photo Polymerisation – Formlabs FLFlex2

Holes are present and have clear definition. Location smallest holes are present but blocked.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
Not present Small dimples	Open 0.48 mm	open 0.78 mm	Open 0.98 mm	Open 2.1 mm	Open 3.05mm

4.8.1 Evaluation: Vertical holes

With Metal Powder Bed Fusion the smallest features can be realized in Titanium and Aluminium, depending on the selected equipment and process parameters. None of the selected polymer based printing processes is capable of realising the smallest Ø 0.25 holes. This is mainly caused by residual material or over exposure.

4.9 Feature: Vertical pillars

Vertical holes and passages are in general of better quality in additive manufacturing than horizontal ones.

Figure 13: Vertical pillars (Z-direction)

Powder Bed Fusion *Industrial* – AlSi10Mg

Ø 0.25 mm pillars are not present. Domed top surface topology.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
Not Present x	present 0.57 mm	present 0.78 mm	present 0.96 mm	present 1.98 mm	present 2.98 mm

Powder Bed Fusion *High Resolution* – AlSi10Mg

All pillars are present. Smallest pillars are slightly bend various directions.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
present 0.28 mm	present 0.60 mm	present 0.82mm	present 1.05mm	present 2.16 mm	present 3.00 mm

Powder Bed Fusion – TiAl6V4

All pillars are present. Smallest pillars are almost straight

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
Present 0.30 mm	Present 0.50 mm	present 0.78 mm	present 1.04 mm	present 2.02 mm	present 3.00 mm

Powder Bed Fusion – PolyAmide PA12

Pillars of Ø 1mm and smaller are missing. Probably too fragile and did not survive the cleaning process.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
not present -	not present -	not present -	not present -	Present ... mm	Present ... mm

Vat Photo Polymerisation - VisiJet

All pillars are present and straight. Clear definition

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
Present 0.22 mm	Present 0.45 mm	Present 0.74 mm	Present 0.97 mm	Present 1.95 mm	Present 2.93mm

Material Jetting – Objet Vero Clear

All pillars are present and straight. Oval shaped. Rounded edges can be detected.

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
Present 0.28 mm	Present 0.54 mm	Present 0.80 mm	Present 1.02 mm	Present 2.00 mm	Present 2.98 mm

Vat Photo Polymerisation – Formlabs FLFlex2

All pillars are present and straight. Clear definition. Pillars of 0.25 and 0.50 mm are bend. Mainly caused due to the flexible material properties

Ø 0.25 mm	Ø 0.50 mm	Ø 0.75 mm	Ø 1.00 mm	Ø 2.00 mm	Ø 3.00 mm
Present 0.18 mm	Present 0.39 mm	Present 0.6 mm	Present 0.91 mm	Present 1.91 mm	Present 2.90 mm

4.9.1 Evaluation: Vertical pillars

The high resolution metal Powder Bed Fusion processes are capable of printing the Ø 0.25 pillars. They are very fragile and slightly bend due to the cleaning process. All pillars are not an issue for Photo Polymerisation based processes. With Polymer PBF the adhesion between the polymer layers is insufficient and they do not survive the cleaning process.

4.10 Feature: Wall Thickness

Vertical wall thickness and spacings are determined laser spot size and melt pool. Side wall quality may cause powder removal problems.

Figure 14: Wall thickness and spacing

Powder Bed Fusion *Industrial* – AlSi10Mg

The outer three rings are free. The middle pillar is fused with the adjacent ring. Domed top surface topology.

Ring 1 Ø7.5 x 0.75 mm	Ring 2 Ø4.5x 0.5 mm	Ring 3 Ø2.5 x 0.35 mm	Ring 4 Ø1.1 x 0.3 mm	Middle Pillar Ø 0.25 mm
Present 7.48 mm	Present 4.5 mm	Present 2.58 mm	fused	

Powder Bed Fusion *High Resolution* – AlSi10Mg

All circles are present and no excess material. Middle pillar of Ø 0.25 mm is present.

Ring 1 Ø7.5 x 0.75 mm	Ring 2 Ø4.5x 0.5 mm	Ring 3 Ø2.5 x 0.35 mm	Ring 4 Ø1.1 x 0.3 mm	Middle Pillar Ø 0.25
Present 7.58 mm	Present 2.54 mm	Present 2.52 mm	Present 1.10 mm	Present 0.34 mm

Powder Bed Fusion – TiAl6V4

All circles are present and no excess material. Middle pillar of \varnothing 0.25 mm is present.

Ring 1 \varnothing 7.5 x 0.75 mm	Ring 2 \varnothing 4.5x 0.5 mm	Ring 3 \varnothing 2.5 x 0.35 mm	Ring 4 \varnothing 1.1 x 0.3 mm	Middle Pillar \varnothing 0.25 mm
Present 7.44 mm	Present 4.54 mm	Present 2.60 mm	Present 1.04 mm	Present 0.40 mm

Powder Bed Fusion – PolyAmide PA12

Only the outer ring is free. Other rings are fused together or blocked by excess material.

Ring 1 \varnothing 7.5 x 0.75 mm	Ring 2 \varnothing 4.5x 0.5 mm	Ring 3 \varnothing 2.5 x 0.35 mm	Ring 4 \varnothing 1.1 x 0.3 mm	Middle Pillar \varnothing 0.25 mm
Present 7.70 mm	Present 4.72 mm	Fused		

Vat Photo Polymerisation - VisiJet

All circles are present and no excess material. Middle pillar of \varnothing 0.25 mm is present. Clear definition.

Ring 1 \varnothing 7.5 x 0.75 mm	Ring 2 \varnothing 4.5x 0.5 mm	Ring 3 \varnothing 2.5 x 0.35 mm	Ring 4 \varnothing 1.1 x 0.3 mm	Middle Pillar \varnothing 0.25 mm
Present 7.65 mm	Present 4.54 mm	Present 2.52 mm	Present 1.02 mm	Partly fused 0.30 mm

Material Jetting – Objet Vero Clear

Most circles are present and no excess material. Middle pillar is fused to the adjacent ring. Rounded corners.

Ring 1 Ø7.5 x 0.75 mm	Ring 2 Ø4.5x 0.5 mm	Ring 3 Ø2.5 x 0.35 mm	Ring 4 Ø1.1 x 0.3 mm	Middle Pillar Ø 0.25
Present 7.54 mm	Present 4.54 mm	Present 2.52 mm	Fused	

Vat Photo Polymerisation – Formlabs FLFlex2

Most circles are present and no excess material. Middle pillar is fused to the adjacent ring. Clear definition.

Ring 1 Ø7.5 x 0.75 mm	Ring 2 Ø4.5x 0.5 mm	Ring 3 Ø2.5 x 0.35 mm	Ring 4 Ø1.1 x 0.3 mm	Middle Pillar Ø 0.25
Present 7.56 mm	Present 4.54 mm	Present 2.50 mm	Present 1.10 mm	Fused (0.28 mm)

4.10.1 Evaluation: wall thickness and spacing

Small spacing may cause fusion between adjacent walls. For polymer processes the minimum acceptable spacing in 0.5 mm. For high resolution metal processes a gap of 0.25 mm is possible in vertical build direction. Narrow and deep slits may cause cleaning issues and leave residual material behind.

4.11 Feature: Horizontal overhang

In additive manufacturing the creation of a horizontal overhang and passages may cause issues if downfacing surfaces are too large and not well supported.

Figure 15: Horizontal bridge

4.11.1 Metal printed parts

Process	Powder Bed Fusion <i>Industrial</i>	Powder Bed Fusion <i>High Resolution</i>	Powder Bed Fusion <i>High Resolution</i>
Material	AlSi10Mg	AlSi10Mg	TiAl6V4
8 x 1 mm 4 x 1 mm			
4 x 1 mm 2 x 1 mm			
Remarks	Extensive sagging and burning of downfacing surfaces. A larger overhang causes more geometrical deviation. With Aluminium, proper heat transfer is not possible and the laser generated melt pool is difficult to control. This results in burning being observed in these areas.	Sagging and burning is observed on downfacing surfaces. Especially in the middle sections of the overhang. The laser melting is better controlled than the Industrial Aluminium PBF process.	Some sagging and burning is observed on downfacing surfaces. The laser melting process can be better controlled using Titanium.

4.11.2 Polymer printed parts

Process	Powder Bed Fusion	Vat Photo Polymerisation	Material Jetting	Vat Photo Polymerisation
Material	PolyAmide PA12	3DSystems VisiJet	Stratasys Objet Vero Clear	FormLabs FLEXP2
8 x 1 mm 4 x 1 mm				
4 x 1 mm 2 x 1 mm				
Remarks	Well defined and proper overhang is being observed. The layers that can be detected are caused by the "Z-Bonus" and are not the build layer thickness of 120 µm.	Limited sagging is observed in horizontal overhang.	Surface roughness is being observed on downfacing surfaces and side walls. The removed soluble support materials has left marks.	Limited sagging and sharp corners. Support pillar is present in middle slot. Automatically generated.

4.12 Feature: Vertical wall thickness

Vertical wall thickness and spacings are determined laser spot size and melt pool. Side wall quality may cause powder removal problems.

Figure 16: Wall thickness and distance

Powder Bed Fusion *Industrial* AlSi10Mg

No clear definition thin wall thicknesses. Smallest open spacing of 0.3 mm is blocked

Dimensions	0.25 x 3.00	0.35 x 3.00	0.50 x 3.00	0.75 x 3.00	1.00 x 3.00
X	0.69 mm	0.66 mm	0.68mm	0.83 mm	1.1 mm
Y	0.70 mm	0.68 mm	0.62 mm	0.84 mm	1.1 mm

Powder Bed Fusion *High Resolution* AlSi10Mg

Clear definition. Open spacing between walls. No hatching at wall thickness of 0.25mm

Dimensions	0.25 x 3.00	0.35 x 3.00	0.50 x 3.00	0.75 x 3.00	1.00 x 3.00
X	0.25 x 3.0	0.37 x 3.0	0.44 x 3.1	0.79 x 3.1	1.1 x 3.13
Y	0.26 x 2.97	0.39 x 3.0	0.54 x 3.05	0.77 x 3.05	1 x 3.09

Powder Bed Fusion TiAl6V4

Clear definition. Open spacing between walls

Dimensions	0.25 x 3.00	0.35 x 3.00	0.50 x 3.00	0.75 x 3.00	1.00 x 3.00
X	0.26 mm	0.38 mm	0.50mm	0.75 mm	0.99 mm
Y	0.22 mm	0.34 mm	0.51 m	0.77 mm	1.01 mm

Powder Bed Fusion – PolyAmide PA12

Barrelled shaped cross section. Small spacings are not present. Wall fused together. Residual powder between walls.

Dimensions	0.25 x 3.00	0.35 x 3.00	0.50 x 3.00	0.75 x 3.00	1.00 x 3.00
X	Fused	Fused	0.85 x 2.74 mm	1.06 x 2.89 mm	1.02 x 3 mm
Y			0.86 x 2.76 mm	0.93 x 2.85 mm	1.10 x 3 mm

Vat Photo Polymerisation – VisiJet

Clear definition. Open spacing between walls

Dimensions	0.25 x 3.00	0.35 x 3.00	0.50 x 3.00	0.75 x 3.00	1.00 x 3.00
X	0.24 x 3 mm	0.28 x 3 mm	0.49 x 3 mm	0.73 x 3 mm	1.0 x 3 mm
Y	0.2 x 3.1 mm	0.33 x 3.1 mm	0.43 x 3.1 mm	0.7 x 3.1 mm	1.0 x 3.1 mm

Material Jetting Stratasys Objet Vero Clear

Rounded edges and surface marks for support structure. Due to overhanging feature above. Residual support material at small wall spacing.

Dimensions	0.25 x 3.00	0.35 x 3.00	0.50 x 3.00	0.75 x 3.00	1.00 x 3.00
X	0.27 x 3.0 mm	0.33 x 3.0 mm	0.46 x 3.1 mm	0.68 x 3.1 mm	1.0 x 3 mm
Y	0.47 x 3.1 mm	0.56 x 3.1 mm	0.79 x 3.1 mm	1.1 x 3.2 mm	1.1 x 3.2 mm

Vat Photo Polymerisation – FormLabs FL Flex2

Sharp and crisp details. Thinnest walls are fused to each other at elevated height.

Dimensions	0.25 x 3.00	0.35 x 3.00	0.50 x 3.00	0.75 x 3.00	1.00 x 3.00
X	0.22 x 3.0 mm	0.28 x 2.96 mm	0.41 x 2.92 mm	0.66 x 2.95 mm	1.0 x 2.9 mm
Y	0.22 x 3.1 mm	0.32 x 3.1 mm	0.44 x 3.1 mm	0.65 x 2.95 mm	0.9 x 2.94 mm

4.12.1 Evaluation: wall thickness and spacing

Small spacing may cause fusion between adjacent walls. For polymer processes the minimum acceptable spacing is 0.5 mm. For high resolution metal processes a gap of 0.25 mm is possible in vertical build direction. Narrow and deep slits may cause cleaning issues and leave residual material behind.

4.13 Angular overhang

A design of inclined plates displays the acceptable angular overhang printed without support. The unsupported surface area: 3 x 4.5mm

Figure 17: Angular overhang.

Metal printed parts

Process	Powder Bed Fusion Industrial	Powder Bed Fusion High Resolution	Powder Bed Fusion
Material	AlSi10Mg	AlSi10Mg	TiAl6V4
Overhang			
15 / 75° 30 / 60°			
Angular overhang			
60/30°	Good surface quality	Good surface quality	Good surface quality
45/45°	Acceptable	Good surface quality	Good surface quality
30 / 60°	Rough surface quality	Acceptable	Acceptable
15/75°	Poor surface quality	Poor surface quality	Acceptable
Remarks	Downfacing surfaces display sagging and rough surface. Quality is decreasing with larger overhanging angle.	Good downfacing surface quality. Large overhanging surface displays some sagging and a slight higher surface roughness.	Good downfacing surface quality. Large overhanging surface displays some sagging and a slight higher surface roughness.

Polymer printed parts

Process	Powder Bed Fusion	Vat Photo Polymerisation	Material Jetting	Vat Photo Polymerisation
Material	PA12	3DSYSTEMS VisiJet	Stratasys Objet Vero Clear	FormLabs FFLex2
Overhang				
15 / 75° 30 / 60°				
Angular Overhang				
60/30°	Good surface quality	Excellent downfacing surface quality	Good surface quality Soluble support marks	Excellent downfacing surface quality
45/45°	Good surface quality	Excellent downfacing surface quality	Good surface quality Soluble support marks	Excellent downfacing surface quality
30 / 60°	Good surface quality	Good surface quality	Acceptable Soluble support marks	Excellent downfacing surface quality
15/75°	Acceptable	Good surface quality	Poor surface quality Soluble support marks	Good surface quality
Remarks	Good quality of downfacing surfaces. Vertical text not present.	Smooth downfacing surfaces. Some support structures present.	Good surface quality. Marks from soluble support structure.	Smooth downfacing surfaces.

4.13.1 Evaluation: Angular overhang

An overhang larger than 45° gives a rough surface and dross formation for metal printed parts. Angles of 45° are therefore ideal. Angles below this value require support structures to ensure the stability of the object during production. The roughness of a down facing surface of a 75° angular overhang is acceptable for most Polymer printing processes.

4.14 Lattice Structures

There are numerous lattice types available as described in section ... of the Cookbook. They can be categorised into four groups:

- 2D Grid
- Periodic / Strut
- Formula driven Lattice
- Stochastic lattice

The design test geometry design comprises four Pie sections that can be filled with different type of lattice structures. The lattice structures used in the current design is a mix of general types that are common in constructional elements and optical components.

Figure 18: the four different lattice structures in the test geometry.

4.14.1 Computer Aided Design

Since no software is available to design all the features of the test geometry, a combination of 3D CAD software packages was used. The main structure is designed in SolidWorks. The Gradient lattice structure is engineered in Autodesk Netfabb. Whereas the Gyroid structure was designed in Gen3D software. Since the latter two are in the STL mesh format, all parts are merged into the final design in Materialise Magics STL editing software.

SolidWorks design with two vacant spots for lattice structures.

Surface model – exported as triangular mesh.

Gyroid design made with Gen3D software – Triangular mesh file.

Graded lattice structure designed with Autodesk Netfabb Triangular mesh file.

The three separate models are merged in Materialise Magics.

Figure 19: 3D CAD Process flow of lattice structure.

4.14.2 Grid structure - Hexagonal Honeycomb.

Honeycomb sandwich structures are designed to have a high stiffness-to-mass ratio. The stiff, strong face sheets carry the bending loads, while the core resists shear loads.

Diagram of an assembled composite sandwich (A), and its constituent face sheets or skins (B) and honeycomb core (C)

For easy residual material removal multiple oval holes are incorporated in the design at the bottom of the cavity.

Figure 20: Grid structures

Process	PBF <i>Industrial</i>	PBF <i>High Resolution</i>	Powder Bed Fusion	Powder Bed Fusion	Vat Photo Polymerisation	Vat Photo Polymerisation
Material	AlSi10Mg	AlSi10Mg	TiAl6V4	PA12	VisiJet	FormLabs Flex
structure						
	Some roundness of corners	Crisp and sharp corners	Crisp and sharp corners	Some roundness of corners	Crisp and sharp corners	Crisp and sharp corners
Top view (XY plane)						
	Wall thickness: 0.51mm Side to side: 3.95mm	Wall thickness: 0.50mm Side to side: 4.05mm	Wall thickness: 0.51mm Side to side: 4.0 mm	Wall thickness: 0.65mm Side to side: 3.85mm	Wall thickness: 0.48mm Side to side: 4.13mm	Wall thickness: 0.48mm Side to side: 4.13mm
Side view ↑ Z build direction						
	Downfacing surface display sagging. Rounded edges. Height: 1.55 mm Width: 0.83 mm	Oval holes display clear definition, slight sagging Height: 1.75 mm Width: 0.90 mm	Oval holes display clear definition Height: 1.85 mm Width: 0.94 mm	More round than oval Height: 1.9 mm Width: 1.2mm	Very clear and crisp definition Height: 2.05 mm Width: 0.95 mm	Very clear and crisp definition Height: 2.05 mm Width: 0.95 mm

4.14.3 Conformal Lattice

A conformal lattice is an ordered structure that follows the surface or set boundaries of a geometry. It prevents loose and open beams. CAD software is used to design a conformal lattice structure with a combination of a Primitive Cubic (cP) and a Body-Centred (BCC) cubic unit cell. The structure in the test geometry is build-up with \varnothing 0.5 mm diameter struts in various directions and angles.

Primitive Cubic consists of one lattice point on each corner of the cub

Body Centred Cubic has one lattice point in the centre of the unit cell in addition to the eight corner points.

The unit cells are conformal to the surface (Nguyen, June 2013).

Round struts with a diameter of 0.5 mm.

Figure 21: Conformal lattice structures

Process	PBF <i>Industrial</i>	PBF <i>High Resolution</i>	Powder Bed Fusion	Powder Bed Fusion	Vat Photo Polymerisation	Vat Photo Polymerisation
Material	AlSi10Mg	AlSi10Mg	TiAl6V4	PA12	VisiJet	FormLabs Flex
Conformal Lattice structure						
	Defect free. All struts present	Defects on largest horizontal struts.	Defects on horizontal struts. Some missing	Defects on diagonal struts. Horizontal struts are present	Defect free. All struts present	Defect free. All struts present
Top view (XY plane)						
	Strut stickness Cp: 0.5 – 0.9 mm BCC: 0.7 – 0.9 mm	Strut stickness Cp: 0.55 mm BCC: 0.5 – 0.65 mm	Strut stickness Cp: 0.5 mm BCC: 0.5 – 0.65 mm	Strut stickness Cp: 0.69mm BCC: 0.64 mm	Strut stickness Cp: 0.44 mm BCC: 0.49 mm	Strut stickness Cp: 0.44 mm BCC: 0.49 mm
Side view ↑ Z build direction						
	All struts are present. Down facing surfaces display sagging and	Some horizontal struts with large overhang are missing or display poor quality	Horizontal struts with large overhang are missing or display poor quality	Multiple angled struts are missing. Horizontal struts are present	All struts are present and of good quality. Some support structures present.	All struts are present and of good quality. Deformation of struts is present in the middle

4.14.4 Gradient Lattice structure

With several 3D software packages it's possible to automatically generate and edit complex lattice structures. Autodesk Netfabb Premium software is used to create a graded volume lattice structure based upon a 3D STL file of the pie-shape. The beams of the structure vary from 0.5 to 1.0 mm in diameter.

Figure 22: Workflow of creating a Gradient lattice structure in Autodesk Netfabb

Process	PBF <i>Industrial</i>	PBF <i>High Resolution</i>	Powder Bed Fusion	Powder Bed Fusion	Vat Photo Polymerisation	Vat Photo Polymerisation
Material	AlSi10Mg	AlSi10Mg	TiAl6V4	PA12	Visijet	FormLabs Flex
Gradient Lattice						
	Defect free. All struts present	Defect free. All struts present	Defect free. All struts present	Defect free. All struts present	Defect free. All struts present	Defect free. All struts present
Top view (XY plane)						
	Rough surface in corners	Clear definition. Some roughness	Clear definition.	Clear definition. Residual powder present	Clear definition.	Clear definition.
Side view ↑ Z build direction						
	Sagging present on downfacing surfaces. Holes partly blocked	Some sagging on downfacing surfaces. Holes are open	Some sagging on downfacing surfaces. Holes are open	Cavities are blocked by residual powder	Clear definition. Support structure is present and cannot be removed	Clear definition. Limited sagging. Holes are open

4.14.5 Formula Drive Lattice – Gyroid structure

There are multiple Triply Periodic Minimal Surfaces structures (TPMS) known. The gyroid is the only known embedded TPMS that possesses triple junctions and no lines of reflectional symmetry. A gyroid surface can be trigonometrically approximated by a short equation:

$$\sin x \cos y + \sin y \cos z + \sin z \cos x = 0$$

The gyroid structure in this example is designed with Gen3D software. This gyroid is self-supporting.

A cubic unit cell of a Schoen's gyroid

The intuitive Gen3D software can be used to generate and manipulate Gyroid lattice structures.

3D STL file of the gyroid mesh with a cell side of 4x4x4 mm

Figure 23: Creation of a formula driven lattice structure with Gen3D.

Process	PBF <i>Industrial</i>	PBF <i>High Resolution</i>	Powder Bed Fusion	Powder Bed Fusion	Vat Photo Polymerisation	Vat Photo Polymerisation
Material	AlSi10Mg	AlSi10Mg	TiAl6V4	PA12	VisiJet	FormLabs Flex
Gyroid Lattice						
	Rounded edges.	Sharp edges, clear definition	Clear definition of structure	Clear definition	Sharp edges, clear definition	Sharp edges, clear definition
Top view (XY plane)						
	Clear shape definition Some splatter	Clear shape definition	Clear shape definition	Clear definition but some residual powder	Clear shape definition	Clear shape definition
Side view ↑ Z direction						
	Downfacing surfaces display large amount of sagging	Downfacing surfaces display sagging	Downfacing surfaces display very slight sagging	Oval shape holes due to Z-bonus. Some residual powder	Non-removed support structure	Clear shape definition Limited sagging

4.14.6 Evaluation of lattice structures

The manufacturability of the four lattice structures is not comparable. The simple, 2,5 D grid structure is suitable for all processes and materials. No support structure is required and the wall thickness of 0.5 mm is not a well achievable. The formula driven Gyroid structure is self-supporting and therefore well suited for both polymer and metal printing. The wall thickness of 1 mm is no issue for the polymer samples. The metal parts display some sagging and dross. All features are present.

The conformal BCC lattice structure with multiple oriented struts is difficult causes difficulties for most processes. The horizontal struts printed with the high resolution metal BPF processes are missing or display large sagging. The horizontal bridging distance of 7 mm is too large. The polymer Vat Photo polymerisation samples are of good quality.

The graded lattice structure is well suitable for all processes. The strut diameter of 0.5 to 1 mm causes no problems. Also the absence of horizontal struts is beneficiary. The metal samples display some dross and sagging.

4.14.7 Assessment of lattices

Figure 24: Assessment of lattice structures for Additive Manufacturing in metal based upon self-supporting properties. The gyroid structure is the best option for metal AM (image credits: VTT).

5 OPTICON TEST GEOMETRY 3D CAD FILE

The 3D CAD file of the Opticon Test Geometry is open source ready. The geometry is available for download from various 3D model file sharing platforms using the “*Opticon*” and /or “*Test Geometry*” search query. The STEP and IGES files are universal CAD formats. Engineers will be able to modify and add features and lattice structures to their own liking. The STL file is suitable for 3D printing.

- GrabCad community
 - <https://grabcad.com/library/opticon-test-geometry-1>
- 3DContentCentral
 - <https://www.3dcontentcentral.com/secure/download-model.aspx?catalogid=171&id=1587498>
- Thingiverse
 - <https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:4893659>

GrabCad Community 3D file sharing platform

3D Content Central by Dassault systems

Thingiverse by Makerbot

Figure 25: The 3D file of the Opticon Test Geometry is free for download from various file sharing platforms.

6 DISCUSSION

The study clearly displays the difference between processes and materials. Also the print results of two parts, build with equal process and material but on different machines have been analysed. The influence of process parameters and the equipment used is clearly visible. The study is far from complete. Various interesting materials and newly developed AM process are existing yet not easy accessible. Additional non-destructive analysis methods are available to examine the parts to further extend.

In addition of measuring the test geometry for geometric accuracy, the print can be analysed to obtain other information about the parts geometry and process. Many areas on the top surface or sides of the part can be examined by a surface profiler to measure the surface roughness. Scanning Electron Microscopy, Computed Tomographic scanning and other 3D imaging technologies are available for non destructive testing and analysis. These methods could deliver valuable information and insight on AM processes and materials. However these technologies are costly and time consuming and are not part of this study.

Microscopic image of the top surface. The hatching pattern and outline are easily detectable.

Confocal Microscopy analysis of the top surface .
200x magnification
Image credits, TNO

Profile - 200x magnification
Ra = 2.5 µm

Figure 26: Surface analysis by Confocal Microscopy of a TiAl6V4 PBF part (image credits TNO).

Dimensional analysis of a feature. The laser scan line are clearly visible

SEM analysis of the top surface of a part with an entrapped ceramic bead
200x magnification

Element detection of the trapped particle shows the material composition. Zirconium Silicate.

Figure 27: Surface analysis by Scanning Electron Microscopy of a TiAl6V4 PBF part (image credits TNO).

7 CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to explain and visualize the overall quality, resolution and capabilities of various Additive Manufacturing principles, systems and materials. The focus was on the design of the artifact and the characterisation of various processes. Besides common design and engineering structures, the test geometry includes interesting features that are found in current optical components and can be put to use in future applications.

It was also important to study how the quality of printed parts are evaluated and measured. The test geometry was tested on 9 different systems and 8 materials. Through a visual inspection it is already possible to obtain conclusions about the capabilities of the system used. The dimensional analysis is done with callipers and with microscopy software.

The analysis showed that the difference in material and the use of dedicated processes influences the overall quality of the end result. More accurate parts are achievable with process and parameter optimisation. Build quality and accuracy are partly effected by the build orientation. Small and thin features are challenging to build regardless the orientation.

Post processing of the manufactured part is not included in the current study. It should also be considered as part of the process development. Part detachment from the building platform, removal of excess material and support structures and cleaning are important steps and effects the outcome.

The Opticon test geometry should be produced using several other AM processes and materials to see if the design is appropriate for those processes as well. Repeatability, variation in material quality and the difference between AM machines and process parameters are important factors to take into account.